

STATIC AND DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF ISOTROPIC AND LAYERED COMPOSITE PLATES - A COMPARATIVE STUDY USING FEM

PARTHASARATHI PAL¹, A. R. CHAUDHURY² & PIJUSH TOPDAR³

^{1,2}Student, Department of Civil Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Durgapur, West Bengal, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Durgapur, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Layered composites comprising of different materials with different combinations such as 0/90/0, and sandwich plates such as f/c/f, 0/90/C/90/0 under static and dynamic loads forms the basis of analysis by conducting experiments or alternatively using Finite Element softwares. This paper includes a brief literature review and some numerical investigations and validation done on isotropic plates, layered composite plates (0/90/0) with varying a/h ratio and sandwich plates(f/c/f, 0/90/C/90/0) under stationary loads with free vibration analysis using commercial FEM software and comparing with standard literatures.

KEYWORDS: Finite Element Softwares, Isotropic Plates & Standard Literatures

INTRODUCTION

The usage of sandwich structures can be dated two thousand years back used by the Chinese. It was Hugo Junkers who brought the idea of laminates with honeycomb core. In 1915 he propounded usage of honeycomb core in aerospace industries and got patented. Composites are extensively in use in aerospace industries but its application has been less in structural engineering applications on deck of bridges. Composites are of different materials (sandwich structures) and same materials of different orientations (0/90, 0/90/0, etc). The advantage of using composites are that it decreases the weight of the structure considerably consequently incurring less cost of the project. As composites finds usage in aircraft industries, they are considered to be reliable. They also have higher ratio in terms of strength to weight. They also have certain drawbacks such as they do generally possess orthotropic mechanical properties 2D in nature, which do not allow them to be used in all applications. They are also not suitable where numerous holes are required. Composites also require fire resistance.

The type of equipment and methods used effect the properties of composites to large extent. Manufacturing difficulties also pose a problem and more attention in the area of composites are required and better implementation in industries by predicting accurate behaviour.

The theory of multilayered structure of stress analysis is properly established. However, despite various theories for sandwich structures, the solutions have been restricted to certain standard geometries.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many literatures have been reported and the void in this area has been filled time and again. J.L. Mantari et al [1] [2] published paper on Static and dynamic analysis of laminated composite and sandwich plates and shells by using a new higher-order shear deformation theory. Topdar et al [3] had given a comprehensive study on refined

higher order shear deformation theories in his paper and also performed vibrational analysis [4]. M.K. Pandit et al [5][6][7] did analysis of laminated structures using improved higher order zigzag theory and penalty function approach for optimization. E. Carrera et al [8] did a survey on classical and refined plate theory with attention to stresses displacements and free vibration analysis. Hirwan did [9] experimental paper on cross plies and Ronald's [10] analysis paper were published based on flexural strength of composite and sandwich structures. A.J.M.Ferreira [11] did analysis of thick, isotropic and laminated cross-ply using Gauss Quadrature techniques at different thickness ratio. Zheng, Liao & Qin [12] published a paper regarding analysis of sandwich structure having honeycomb core to be used for Micro satellite based on 'Equivalent Theory'. Natarajan, Haboussi & Manickam [13] used CNT reinforced composite face sheets for analysis of bending and shear in plates. MohmadBelarbi et al [14] performed 2-D model analysis of using isoparametric coordinates and layer wise approach for bending. Slimane[15] and Kreja[16] did a comprehensive study on different theories of plates with computational models. M. C'etkovic et al [17] used layer wise displacement model for bending, free vibration and buckling analysis of laminated composite and sandwich plates.

Thus comprehensive study has been done in this field and to substantiate these theories and results some numerical examples has been shown below.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Example 1

A rectangle isotropic plate of dimension 300mm X 200mm X 30mm subjected to a uniform distributed load of 100N/m^2 was studied having the following material properties. Young's modulus (E) =200GPa, density (ρ) =7850kg/m³, Poisson's ratio (μ) =0.3

Table 1: Results Obtained in present Study and Comparison with Timoshenko Plate Theory [19]

Fixity/Boundary Condition	Displacement in Present Study(m)	Displacement in Timoshenko Plate Theory(m)[19]	% Difference
C-C-C-C	7.094E-7	7.108E-7	0.19
S-S-S-S	1.248E-6	1.251E-6	0.24
F-C-C-C	9.515E-7	9.552E-7	0.38
F-S-S-S	1.923E-6	1.924E-6	0.05

Example 2

A rectangular isotropic plate of following details were studied for free vibration analysis

Material used: Aluminum

Dimension: 49.5cm x 36.1cm Properties of the material

- Young's Modulus of Elasticity (E): 70GPa
- Density (ρ): 2700kg/m³
- Poisson's ratio (μ): 0.33
- Boundary Condition: CCCC (clamped in all direction)

Table 2: Comparison of Eigen Frequencies (Hz) Between Present Study and Experimental Study [18]

Mode No.	Present Study (Hz)	Experimental Study (Hz)[18]	% Difference
1	148.51	153	2.93
2	244.15	240	1.73
3	353.26	373	5.29
4	402.6	414	2.75
5	441.68	449	1.63

Example 3

A 0/90/C/90/0 sandwich plate is studied under free vibration analysis with two boundary conditions (i)clamped in all directions(CCCC) (ii)two opposite sides clamped and other two sides simply supported(SCSC). The material properties used are as follows

Ply of Face Sheet: $E_{11}/E=40.0$, $E_{22}/E=1.0$, $E_{33}=E_{22}$, $G_{12}/E=G_{13}/E=G_{23}/E$, $\mu_{12}=0.25$, $\mu_{13}=0.5$, $\mu_{23}=0.3$, $\rho_f = \rho$

Core: $E_c/E=0.0837$, $G_{c12}/E=G_{c13}/E=0.0156$, $G_{c23}/E=0.0322$, $\mu_{c12}=\mu_{c13}=\mu_{c23}=0.0025$, $\rho_c/\rho=1.4667$

The analysis is carried out using $a/h=10.0, 5.0$ and compared with P. Topdar et al[17]

Figure 1: Single Core Sandwich (f(0/90)/c/f(90/0)) with Laminated Face Sheet

Table 3: Frequency Parameters [$\Omega = 100\omega a \sqrt{(\rho_c/E_{11})}$] of a Square Sandwich Plate with Laminated Face Sheets (f(0/90)/C/f(90/0)) with Different Boundary Conditions

a/h Boundary	References	Mode Number					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
CCCC	4x4	13.71	19.92	20.11	26.23	28.01	36.34
	8x8	12.75	15.93	17.94	22.84	24.79	29.21
	12x12	12.45	14.66	17.54	22.12	24.11	28.35
Present Study	16x16	12.31	14.02	17.37	18.99	21.80	23.88
	18x18	12.27	13.8	17.32	21.7	23.82	27.95
	20x20	12.23	13.62	17.28	21.62	23.77	27.89
P.Topdar et al[17]		11.47	17.14	19.53	23.69	24.32	29.02
10	4X4	15.8	20.38	23.05	24.96	26.18	30.6
	8X8	13.41	19.16	22.52	22.9	22.97	23.37
SCSC	12X12	12.99	18.44	20.23	22.19	22.73	22.94
	Present	16X16	12.51	18.0	18.87	21.78	22.52

Table 3: Contd.,

Study	18X18	12.1	17.82	18.35	21.63	22.47	22.92
	20X20	11.61	17.64	17.85	21.48	22.43	22.81
	23X23	11.51	16.48	17.13	21.08	22.39	22.91
P.Topdar et al[17]		10.94	16.24	19.2	22.8	22.86	23.7

Table 4

a/h	Boundary	References	Mode Number						
			1	2	3	4	5	6	
5	CCCC	4X4	19.1	47.43	50.04	110.1	110.41	116.39	
		8X8	12.22	20.53	24.81	32.69	36.19	39.17	
		Present	12X12	11.79	15.02	17.96	19.93	24.12	25.55
		Study	16X16	11.54	17.55	19.67	23.91	25.32	26.91
			18X18	11.74	17.65	19.86	23.97	25.32	27.97
			20X20	11.69	17.61	19.77	23.88	25.28	27.81
			P.Topdar et al[17]	12.42	19.13	21.46	26.95	28.25	32.43
		SCSC	4X4	14.05	23.99	28.36	32.67	50.45	52.76
	Present		8X8	12.28	16.61	21.63	24.76	27.53	29.46
		Study	12X12	11.83	17.78	19.99	24.23	25.65	28.21
		16X16	11.82	17.72	20.01	24.06	24.21	25.39	
		P.Topdar et al[17]	11.78	17.43	20.98	23.7	25.23	25.29	

Example 4

A cross-ply (0/90/0) rectangular composite laminated plate simply supported at the four edges is analyzed with an element (a x b x h) using a number of mesh sizes. The aspect ratio $b/a = 1$. The value of the deflections are compared at $a/2$, $b/2$ with Topdar-et-al [3] at $a/h=4$ and $a/h=10$. $E1/E2=25$, $G12=G13=0.5E2$, $G23=0.2E2$, $\mu_{12}=0.25$.

The analysis is done in COMSOL 5.2a (Present Study) for $a/h=4$ and $a/h=10$.

Table 5: For a/h=4

Present Study(mm)	RHS DT(mm)[3]	% Difference	Mesh Size
3.0619	3.0244	1.24	38 X 38

Table 6: For a/h=10

Present Study(mm)	RHS DT(mm)[3]	% Difference	Mesh Size
1.1703	1.1582	1.02	40 X 40

Example 5

A simply supported single core (f/c/f) square ($b/a=1$) sandwich plate ($a= 0.254m$) having thickness is 20.4724mm is subjected to uniformly distributed load ($q=6.895kPa$) is analyzed using different mesh sizes. The thickness of the faces is 0.7112mm and core is

Face: $E_x = 68950e6$ Pa; $E_y = 27500e6$ Pa; $E_z = 27500e6$ Pa; $G_{xy} = 27500e6$ Pa; $G_{xy} = G_{yz} = 10000e6$ Pa; $G_{xy} = 10300e6$ Pa; $\mu_{xy} = \mu_{yz} = \mu_{zx} = 0.30$.

Core: $E_x = E_y = E_z = 689.5e6$ Pa; $G_{xy} = 82.74e6$ Pa; $G_{yz} = 82.74e6$ Pa; $G_{zx} = 206.85e6$ Pa

$\mu_{xy} = \mu_{yz} = \mu_{zx} = 0.30$

The analysis was done in both COMSOL 5.2a (Present Study1) and ANSYS-19(Present Study2) and compared with Topdar-et-al [3]

Table 7: Displacements Obtained in Present Study 1

Present Study1(mm)	Analytical(mm)[3]	% Difference	Mesh Size
0.326	0.314	3.82	28 X 28

Table 8: Displacements Obtained in Present Study 2

Present Study2(mm)	Analytical(mm)[3]	% Difference	Mesh Size
0.325	0.314	3.5	18 X 18

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn after the numerical study and validation was performed

- In case of static analysis, the results obtained in isotropic plate (Example 1) on different boundary conditions are in agreement with Timoshenko theory [19] with a maximum percentage difference of 0.38% which suggests that the modeling and accuracy of the software is fine and can be used for further numerical investigation purposes.
- In case of static analysis of composite laminated plates (Example 4) and sandwich plates (Example 5) results were in agreement with Topdar et al [3] showing a maximum percentage difference to the tune of 1.24% for composite (0/90/0) plate and 3.82% for sandwich plate(f/c/f) and can be used for comparison with future studies both analytically and experimentally.
- As far as free vibration analysis on isotropic plate is concerned (Example 2) frequencies obtained were found to be showing a maximum deviation of 5.29% at mode 3 which suggests a satisfactory agreement with experimental study [19] and adequacy of the software is also satisfactory for performing vibration analysis for composite sandwich plates.
- Free vibration analysis results on laminated composite sandwich plates performed (Example 3) with various boundary conditions were validated with P.Topdar et al [17] and frequencies obtained were satisfactory.

Hence the overall comparison study shows that the results are analogous to the standard results available in literatures. It can also be ascertained that COMSOL 5.2a is a useful software to perform computations at shorter time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to thank the library facility, research unit of Department of Civil Engineering for helping me preparing this paper.

REFERENCES

1. Mantari, J. L., Oktem, A. S., & Soares, C. G. "Static and dynamic analysis of laminated composite and sandwich plates and shells by using a new higher-order shear deformation theory". *Composite Structures* Vol-94,(2011). 37-49.
2. J.L.Mantari, A. S. Oktem, C.Guedes Centre for Marine Technology Engineering(CENTEC), Technical University of Lisbon. "Bending and free vibration analysis of isotropic and multilayered plates and shells by using a new accurate higher order shear deformation". *Composites:Part B* 43,(2012), 3348-3360
3. Topdar, P., Sheikh, A. K., & Dhang, N. "Finite Element Analysis of Composite and Sandwich plates Using a Continuous Inter-laminar Shear Stress Model."(SAGE), *Journal of sandwich structures and materials*, Vol. 5, (2003),207-231.
4. Pandit, M. K., Haldar, S., & Mukhopadhyay, M. "Free vibration analysis of laminated composite rectangular plate using finite element method." *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites (SAGE Publications)* Vol. 26, No. 1 (2007), 69-80.
5. Pandit, M. Sheikh, A. H., & Singh, B. N.. "An improved high order zig-zag theory for the statistical analysis of laminated sandwich plate with soft core". *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design (ELSEVIER)*, Volume 44 Issue 9-10(2008), 602-610.
6. Pandit, M. K., Singh, B. N., & Sheikh, A. H., "Stochastic Free Vibration Response of Soft Core Sandwich Plates Using an Improved Higher-Order Zigzag Theory". *Journal of Aerospace Engineering/Vol-23(1) (ASCE publication)(2010)*, 14-23.
7. E. Carrera, S.Brischetto, "A survey with numerical assessment of Classical and Refined Theories for the analysis of Sandwich plates," *American Society of Mechanical Engineering (Applied Mechanics Review)DOI: 10.1115/1.3013824*, Vol. 62, (2009)
8. Hirwani, C. K., & Panda, S. K, " Flexural strength of delaminated composite plate-An experimental validation, *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*" (SAGE),(2016), 1-34.
9. Ronald. F. Gibson, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Nevada, Reno, MS-312, Reno, NV 89557, United States,"A review on recent research of mechanics of multifunctional composite materials and structures.(ELSEVIER),*Science Direct, Composite Structures* 92 (2010) 2793–2810
10. Ferreria, A. J., Carrera, E., Cinefra, M., Viola, E., Tornabene, F., Fantuzzi, N., et al. (2014). "Analysis of thick isotropic and cross-ply laminated plates by generalized differential quadrature method and a Unified Formulation." *ScienceDirect (Composites:Part-B Engineering)* Vol-58, 544-552.
11. Zheng, K., Liao, W. H., & Qin, Y. T.. *Analysis and Research of Honeycomb Sandwich Structure for MicroSatellite Based on Equivalent Theory. Scientific.Net*, Vols. 426-427, (2010), 472-476.
12. Natarajan, S., Haboussi, M., & Manickam, G. Application of higher-order structural theory to bending and free vibration analysis of sandwich plates with CNT reinforced composite facesheets. *ELSEVIER (Composite Structures)* 113,(2014) 197-207.
13. Belarbi Mohamed Ouejdi, TatiAbdelouahab, OunisHoudayfa, Benchabane Adel, Laboratoire de GénieEnergétiqueetMatériaux, LGEM. Université de Biskra, B.P. 145, R.P. 07000, Biskra, Algeria "Development of 2D isoparametric finite element model based on layerwise approach for bending analysis of sandwich plates. *Structural Engineering and Mechanics*, Vol.-57, No. 3 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.12989/sem.2016.57.3.473> (2016), 473-506
14. Slimane, M. "Study and comparison of different plate theory". *International Journal of Engineering Research And Advanced Technology (IJERAT)*, E-ISSN-2454-6135,(2017),Vol-3(8) 48-59.
15. IreneuszKreja,"A literature review on computational models for laminated composites and sandwich panels". *Central European Journal of Engineering (VERSITA)*,(2011) 59-80

16. M. C'etkovic', Dj. Vuksanovic, Faculty of Civil Engineering, University of Belgrade, Bul. kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia "Bending, Free vibrations and buckling of laminated composite and sandwich plates.using a layerwise displacement model", (ELSEVIER), Science Direct, Composite Structure 88 (2009) 219-227
17. P.Topdar, A.H.Sheikh, N. Dhang "Vibration characteristics of composite/sandwich laminates with piezoelectric layers using a refined hybrid plate model" International Journal of Mechanical Sciences, 49(11)(2007) ELSEVIER, 1193-1203
18. Amit Jha. Free vibration analysis of sandwich panel.(2007), thesis submitted for partial fulfillment of award of M.tech degree from National Institute of technology, Rourkela
19. Theory of Plates and Shells by Timoshenko, 3rd edition, MacGraw Hill publishers.